

CLINICAL SYMPTOMS OF CHRONIC TONSILLITIS TOXICO-ALLERGIC FORM, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT METHODS

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Abstract. Tonsillitis is usually caused by a viral infection. If you have tonsillitis, you'll probably have a sore throat. But a sore throat isn't always due to tonsillitis. To see if you have tonsillitis, a GP will examine your throat and tonsils.

Keywords: Tonsillitis viral, infection, high temperature, bad breath, headache, feeling generally unwell, feeling sick or vomiting, tummy pain.

КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ТОНЗИЛЛИТА ТОКСИКО-АЛЛЕРГИЧЕСКОЙ ФОРМЫ, МЕТОДЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ

Аннотация. Тонзиллит обычно вызывается вирусной инфекцией. Если у вас тонзиллит, у вас, скорее всего, будет болеть горло. Но боль в горле не всегда является следствием тонзиллита. Чтобы определить, есть ли у вас тонзиллит, врач общей практики осмотрит ваше горло и миндалины.

Ключевые слова: вирусный тонзиллит, инфекция, высокая температура, неприятный запах изо рта, головная боль, общее недомогание, тошнота или рвота, боль в животе.

• What is tonsillitis?

• Tonsillitis means you have swollen (inflamed) tonsils. Your tonsils are two small round lumps of tissue at the back of your throat. You may have a sore throat, swollen tonsils, and pain when you swallow.

What causes tonsillitis?

Tonsillitis is usually caused by a viral infection. Viruses causing tonsillitis include:

- the common cold virus
- the flu virus (influenza)

For around one in every three people, tonsillitis is caused by bacteria. Most bacterial tonsillitis is caused by streptococcus bacteria – specifically group A beta-haemolytic streptococcus bacteria. This is sometimes called 'strep throat'.

Is tonsillitis contagious?

Tonsillitis itself isn't contagious. Tonsillitis is often caused by cold and flu viruses that you can catch. You may also get tonsillitis if streptococcal bacteria affect your throat.

Symptoms of tonsillitis

If you have tonsillitis, you'll probably have a sore throat. But a sore throat isn't always due to tonsillitis.

Other symptoms of tonsillitis may include:

- pain when swallowing
- finding it hard to swallow
- earache
- high temperature (over 38°C)
- bad breath
- headache
- feeling generally unwell
- feeling sick or vomiting
- tummy pain

You may also notice that you have swollen tonsils and swollen glands in your neck. Your tonsils may be covered with a white coating or white flecks of pus.

Tonsillitis symptoms are similar to glandular fever symptoms. [Glandular fever](#) is a viral infection affecting mostly teenagers and young adults. Your GP may ask you to have a blood test if they suspect glandular fever.

Should I see my GP about a sore throat?

You don't normally need to see a GP about a sore throat. Tonsillitis usually gets better within a week without needing to visit a GP. But if you're worried about symptoms, or they don't improve, see a GP.

Diagnosis of tonsillitis

To see if you have tonsillitis, a GP will examine your throat and tonsils. They may:

- use a bright torch to see the inside of your mouth better
- use a tongue depressor to push your tongue down gently
- feel around your neck to see if you have swollen glands

Treatment of tonsillitis

Most people find that tonsillitis symptoms improve with self-help. Antibiotics won't work if your tonsillitis is caused by a viral infection. A GP may give antibiotics for tonsillitis if:

- your symptoms are very bad, such as severe bacterial infection
- you could be prone to serious complications (see our section on complications)

GPs usually prescribe a 5 to 10-day course of penicillin. Tell your GP if you're allergic to penicillin so they can give you a different antibiotic.

It's important to take antibiotics properly. Complete the full course, even if you start to feel better. This helps to get rid of the bacteria and reduces the risk of antibiotic resistance (when antibiotics no longer work against the bacteria). Read the patient information leaflet carefully and see a pharmacist if you have questions.

Do I need surgery for tonsillitis?

A GP may refer you to an ear, nose, and throat (ENT) surgeon if you need your tonsils removed. This operation is called a [tonsillectomy](#).

Some people get tonsillitis again and again. This is called recurrent tonsillitis and may be a reason to consider tonsil removal by tonsillectomy.

Your doctor may also recommend tonsillectomy if you've had abscess on your tonsils. This can be a complication of tonsillitis.

For children, your GP may recommend waiting for tonsillitis to get better on its own before considering surgery. As children get older, they are less likely to have tonsillitis.

Complications of tonsillitis

Tonsillitis usually doesn't cause long-term problems. Severe infection or complications are more likely if you have a weak immune system. Complications are also more common in young children and older people.

Bacterial tonsillitis can sometimes lead to a build-up of pus on or around your tonsils. This is called a peritonsillar abscess or quinsy. This may cause very bad throat pain, often worse on one side. You may also have other symptoms, which include:

- earache
- high temperature
- difficulty swallowing due to pain
- difficulty opening your mouth

Peritonsillar abscess is more common in teenagers and young adults. But children can get it too. The abscess is usually treated with antibiotics and surgery to drain the pus.

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